

Examining the Trauma of Male Rape Victims within the Last 30 Years:

Rape Myths, Victim Blaming & Under-Reporting.

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Abstract

Male rape is a taboo topic that is only recently gaining more popularity as a research subject. In the UK it took a heinous crime like the one of Sinaga to prompt wider critical thinking about current misconceptions of what is meant by male rape. The purpose of this study was to examine and conduct a library-based research project highlighting some of the academic studies about male rape. This was achieved by using a variety of mixed media, such as journals, articles, interviews, and websites. The project examined the under reporting of male rape by using statistics from the Crime Survey of England and Wales. This project also explored how blaming the victim is ingrained in rape culture. This research also highlights the issues that male rape myths create for victims and examines some elements of trauma that male rape victims face. The findings of this essay revealed that there is a large gap between the number of sexual assaults in the Crime Survey for England and Wales and the number of reports to the police. This project also brings to light that there are still male rape myths that plague society to this day. Rape myths, trauma and victim blaming highly correlate with male victims feeling like they cannot report the crime. This research has shown that further research into the subject of male rape would be beneficial.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Rape is recognised as a serious and brutal crime globally, but it is widely under-reported in all its domains. There are numerous reasons why this crime is under-reported, and this can be connected to the ways in which rape is understood and defined. How it is understood takes the shape of certain conceptions of rape, and also the broad operations of sex role socialisation, that assists us in being able to recognise particular acts as rape (Pino & Meier, 1999).

Historically, the topic of adult men being sexual victims was considered impossible and if not that, extremely rare. Due to this, services for male survivors were seen as needless and stayed as an under developed provision compared to those for female survivors (Lowe & Rogers, 2017). In 1994, the criminal justice and public order act revised rape within English law. This revision included males as victims as well as females (Doherty & Anderson, 2004). Up until then, the UK law ceased to acknowledge male-on-male rape as a criminal violation. If we look at the revised law it consists of the Sexual Offences Act, which defines rape as a deliberate penile penetration of the vagina, anus, and mouth without consent (Spruin, 2018). Other changes have also been made for example, since consent is deemed by law, children, adolescents, and endangered people are guarded more. However, it is also argued that previous changes are potentially excluding or missing out on morally criminal sexual acts of present social-legal importance (Russell & Hand, 2017).

Almost 1 in 5 women reported encountering attempted or completed rape within their lifetime. This number is much higher compared to 1 in 71 men reporting sexual violence, 24.8 percent of men report encountering some form of sexual violence during their lifetime, whether it be sexual contact that involves constraint, intimidation or a difference in power (Smith et al., 2018). It is possible that these rates may be much higher if the definitions of rape were corrected to “forced to penetrate” (Foster & Bock, 2023). There is now a various number of services for male rape survivors in England and Wales, even so, there are still social, emotional, and cultural obstacles that obstruct men from reporting and searching for help, which means that certain victims are not directed to the best service to oversee their needs. This creates a varied amount of problems; firstly, being that these victims may feel alone and emotionally impaired. Secondly, society as a whole will continue to challenge the reality of male rape (Javaid, 2018). Research since the mid-1990s, especially over the last 10 years, has started to investigate the occurrence, range, and ramifications of male rape and sexual victimisation. New designs for services and how they help male victims are identified as crucial (Lowe & Rogers, 2017).

A shocking case of the serial rapist, Reynhard Singa, who was convicted between 2018 and 2020 for raping 48 men in the UK. He is believed to have raped more than 200 other men in total. His crime has brought attention to the urgent need to broaden the focus on inclusivity when conducting research on adult sexual assault (Langdridge et al, 2023). This case is what inspired the idea for this research report. The overall aim of this research report seeks to explore the concept of victim blame, judgments towards male rape, manifestations of male rape myths prevalent in Western society, and male and female rape reporting behaviour. Including an in-depth analysis of the rape reports using data from the Crime Survey of England and Wales.

Chapter 2: Methodology

This research project is exploring and critically analysing literature on Male rape issues and the impact it has on the victim. This was a Library/desk-based project using literature that used qualitative and quantitative information (also known as mixed methods) and was gathered using a variety of academic journals and books discussing male rape myths, consisting of interviews with victims, academic research, and case studies (Bryman, 2016).

Mixed methods were appropriate for this research because it offers more perspective towards this research, it will enable the use of numeric and narrative data which will offer a more in-depth understanding of the research question and will also consist of credible and trustworthy sources and internal and external valid data (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2020).

Ontology focuses on the nature of reality and social entities (Bryman, 2016). It proposes that there is no correct way to ontologically understand the social world and instead, there are a variety of ontologies or varied understandings of reality and each one has validity. Overall, this ontological attitude means that decent research practice should be prioritised instead of obsessing with ontological considerations. For example, researching female rape offenders by looking at statical data is considered legitimate and truthful but you can also gather legitimate and truthful data from interviewing female prisoners. These truths are equally reasonable and various realities welcome this aligning them together (Davies et al, 2018). This was attempted in the project by using statistical data as well as interviews and questionnaires which added more depth to the research.

Secondary research is the primary method used to collect research on this topic. Secondary research is used to analyse existing data and does not require the collection of primary empirical data (Booth et al, 2016). There are a few secondary research methods: re-analysis of current data (such as published police data, crime survey books, and peer-reviewed articles) or analysis of current literature (such as reports, Newspapers, media articles, and policy documents). Compared to secondary research, collecting primary research depends on the essence of the research, the research question, and the methodological substructure. It is highlighted that methods can be vastly categorized as either quantitative or qualitative, but in execution, this contrast is not always reflective of the method.

An example of this is questionnaires and surveys, which have originally been considered quantitative methods and normally consist of closed questions; however, questionnaires and surveys with open questions can produce qualitative data. Other kinds of primary research include interviews, experiments, and visual methods such as photography and props (Davies et al, 2018).

This was the best way to gather information because male rape is a sensitive topic and without the researcher having proper training on how to conduct interviews it would be very likely that the researcher would re-traumatise victims and put them in an uncomfortable position (Javaid, 2015). The researcher was also not close to anyone who was male and a victim of rape and had no access to male victims so it would be very unrealistic to try and do primary research. These issues ultimately helped to rule out using primary research.

One critique of using secondary research for this topic is the amount of quality literature and academic journals on this topic. Initially, the researcher assumed it would be quite easy to gather information on the topic but there is still a wide gap, it requires a lot more digging through the web and libraries to find academic information about male rape. Overall, most of the information found about male rape was fairly old, there were a few occasional more recent articles. Another issue that the researcher faced was finding data only based in the UK. Male rape only started to gain more notoriety during the mid-90s (Lowe & Rogers, 2017). So therefore, there are fewer academic studies on this topic especially in the UK (Javaid, 2018). The researcher combatted this by changing the title of the project, so it did not specify it as being only based in the UK. This enabled the researcher to find much more empirical studies about the culture of male rape, looking at studies based in other European countries and America.

Ethical concerns are at the center of social research and are crucial principles that notify and create research practice. Acknowledging ethical issues of criminological research is crucial and it is important that these ethical issues are examined preceding at during the research process. Most departments have established ethical guidelines in criminology, these guidelines are provided by the British Society of Criminology and the British Psychological Society (Davies et al, 2018).

The BSC has a code of ethics that groups together important ethical responsibilities into five sections: general authority, the authority of the researchers approaching the discipline of criminology; researchers' responsibilities to their colleagues; researchers' authority towards the research candidates, and relationships with advocates. The biggest category examines the responsibilities towards the research candidates in regard to their physical social and psychological well-being as well as data protection.

Violating the privacy of participants involved in studies is something that the researcher wanted to avoid, when looking into academic studies no names or identifying information of the participants was available. Because the academic journals used in the project were made available publicly, there was no need for consent from the participants (Neuman, 2014). However, the researcher acknowledges that if any personal interviews were conducted a consent form would have needed to be signed (Bryman, 2016).

All research projects done in universities need to go through internal ethical consent which normally comprises of completing an ethics form, explaining the project, and listing key ethical issues and how they can be addressed. A panel will then critique and decide whether enough consideration has been given to all the problems identified with the research project (Booth et al, 2016). The ethical standard that the researcher had to adhere to was similar to this as it was done by completing a research proposal this proposal needs to state the purpose of the research and how it would be executed, it would then be signed off by the researcher's allocated supervisor.

When researching a sensitive subject such as rape there are a lot of ethical factors that need to be considered. The victim's safety and confidentiality need to be considered and the researcher needs to be skilled in how to communicate with the victims to avoid re-traumatisation (SVRI, 2020). These standards seem to be rather impractical for an undergraduate student to be able to follow so therefore, library-based research was the best approach for this project.

Chapter 3: Is Male Rape Under Reported?

In this section, the under reporting of rape will be explored. Key quantitative data will be presented alongside academic literature exploring why male rape is not reported as often.

The Crime Survey for England and Wales (CSEW) revealed that in the year ending 2020, there were roughly around 773,000 adults aged 16-74 that experienced sexual assault (including attempts) with 618,000 female victims and 155,000 male victims. An estimation from the crime survey disclosed that 16 percent of female victims and 19 percent of male victims aged 16-59 were assaulted via penetration or rape and reported it (CSEW, 2021).

In comparison, January 2013, was when the first official statistics about sexual violence were released by the Ministry of Justice. In the year ending March 2014, around 85,000 women and 12,000 men between the ages of 16-59 reported having experienced rape or sexual assault resulting in attempted rape by penetration. Out of those people, only 15 percent reported their incidents to the police. Around 90 percent of those raped knew the perpetrator previously to the offense (SOSRC, 2021).

If we look at the most recent data from the Crime Survey of England and Wales, we can see that roughly 1.1 million adults aged 16+ have been victims of sexual assaults in 2022 (798,000 women and 275,000 men). Even though there were no substantial changes in the number of assaults that adults aged 16-59 experienced within the last year (2.7 percent) compared to the year ending March 2020 (2.2 percent) if comparisons are made to the year ending March 2014 (1.5 percent) there has been a substantial increase. This correlates with the movements among police recorded crime. Within the last decade, there has been an increase in sexual offenses being recorded by police. However, the numbers are still low compared to the numbers reflected in the survey. The most recent figure ending March 2022 shows a growth of 31 percent to 193,566 recorded offences compared to last year (CSEW, 2023).

There has definitely been a heightened media interest in sexual crimes committed against men, which have influenced some men to take their stories to social media and seek help for their assault. It's still the case that officially reported sexual crimes are still not accurately reflecting actual offence rates. Numerous men never discuss their assault with anyone and do not seek support in the distant future. It seems from the literature that researchers can see there is a large gap in relation to reporting of

sexual offences against men (Lowe & Rogers, 2017). Many men who fell victim to rape do not realise what occurred is rape and have not got the right vocabulary to describe their assault, as it's not considered in the legal institution. The lack of acknowledgment in the legal system in regard to forced acts such as male sexual assault with a bottle or finger, instead of just penile is an issue as various male victims classify acts such as this as rape. When rape among males is not seen as a serious issue this can reflect in the way that police record alleged male rape. This means that certain assaults against males would be categorised as not being a crime due to fallible understanding and misconceptions about male rape (Javaid, 2018).

Artime et al. (2014), conducted a study on 323 men who took part in an online survey, this survey revealed that only 24 percent of rape victims used the terms of rape and sexual abuse. Most of the participants did not feel that what happened to them was a major sexual infraction worth reporting to the police, leading to no further investigations being made (Hammond et al, 2016). This reluctant mindset from men could be fuelled by the issue of modern cultures (especially in Western culture, as this is where most research is based) and a lack of understanding about the magnitude of male rape and sexual abuse. Due to this, victims may have a hard time realising their own victimisation (Cermak & Molitor, 1996; Blanchard, 1986). Fisher and Pina (2013), argued that predisposed legal definitions, feminist theories, stereotypes, and myths fuel a troublesome environment for male survivors to report their assaults (Hammond et al, 2016). An organisation called Survivors UK specializes in helping male rape victims by providing support and therapy. This organisation conducted a research report on its users and found that only 3.9 percent of male victims reported their assault in 2015 and in 2022 the report found that 2,673 people used their national helpline for general support (Survivors UK, 2022).

The case of Sinaga who was jailed in 2020 after being convicted of drugging and raping 48 men in his Manchester flat. This case highlights the issues of under-reporting among male rape victims. Police were able to identify the 48 victims due to recorded footage found on Sinaga's phone with hundreds of hours of footage (most victims were unaware that they were raped due to being drugged). However, due to the evidence police believe that there are at least 200 more victims of Sinaga (BBC, 2021). Considering how prolific this case is, it's surprising only two small-scale documentaries were made about this case. *Catching a Predator* and *Surviving Sinaga* (IMDb, 2020). Sinaga was convicted in 2020 for 159 offences (BBC, 2021).

In addition to this case in March 2020, the Crime Survey for England and Wales revealed that around 618,000 women and 155,000 men aged 16-74 have been victims of sexual assault. This is around 3 in 100 women and 1 in 100 men (CSEW, 2021). The numbers show that male assaults are significantly

lower than for women. However, it's still a considerable number of victims. There is a high chance that the numbers are much higher than what is shown due to the fact that male rape victims are hesitant to report their assaults or don't understand that they have been raped (Langdridge et al, 2023).

Women often have to battle rape myths whether it be from society or in a court setting, such as what they were wearing or how late at night they were out (Cook & Hodo, 2013). It might be expected that the reasons for men reporting their assault would align with those for women, but it is important to consider the possible differences in how males' function (Groth and Burgess, 1980). Male rape is depicted more commonly in the artificial environment of prison life and certain violent characteristics of homosexual subculture (Kaufman et al., 1980). Psychological trauma can impact and inhibit victims to report due to embarrassment and shock. A lot of men tend to hide and regulate their negative emotions (Kaufman et al., 1980). McRae et al (2008) believed it could be argued that this is because men are able to use regulation with greater efficiency, or less effort than women because men showed greater down-regulation of amygdala activity and less prefrontal activity during regulation (McRae et al, 2008).

There is also the aspect of gender role expectations, which deem it unmanly for a man to express emotion even when they are under severe physical or psychological distress. Reports of male rape are statically rare, this can also contribute to male victims not wanting to report their crimes as there are not as many open victims they can relate to, partnered with the idea that they have lost their sense of masculinity (Adler, 1992).

Research has also shown that male rape victims are more likely to be assaulted by multiple victims, experience more physical trauma, and be held hostage longer than women (Kaufman et al., 1980). Circumstances like these can almost guarantee low rape reporting and ultimately reporting a rape to the police is equally as stressful for men as it is for women (Groth and Burgess, 1980).

Chapter 4: Male Rape Myths

4.1 Introduction

Rape myths are one of the unfortunate ways that sexual aggression has been justified in society. And up until now, there has been a lack of research concerning male victims (Lowe & Rogers, 2017). As established rape is quite a sensitive and taboo topic to talk about and there are many myths about rape that are extremely generalised and incorrect. This chapter aims to identify some of these myths and debunk them using academic literature. This will be achieved by reviewing some societal misconceptions, institutionalised stereotypes, and media perspectives.

Academic research on male and female rape normally centralises cognitive distortions that occur in the forms of attitudes that support rape. These attitudes ease the way for justifying sexual violence, blaming the victims, removing responsibility from the perpetrator, decreasing the number of people who come forward claiming rape, and implying that only a certain type of woman is raped (Fawcett Society, 2017). Common examples of rape myths are believing that a woman is partially responsible or completely responsible for their rape if they were out late, wearing tops with cleavage or a short skirt, and if they are drunk (Survivors UK, 2022). In a UK report, they found that 38 percent of men and 34 percent of women shared these rape myth views (Yapp & Quayle, 2018; Fawcett Society, 2017). Many sex crimes that occur tend to be committed against women, but sexual assault can be performed by both men and women. Men are more likely to be offenders and women are more likely to be victims, but research tends to focus on the majority leaving a gap for research in regards to men's sexual assaults and seeing men as only being offenders and women victims (Robertson, 2010).

The criticism and anonymity of male sexual assault is mostly due to the longevity of rape myths which are often defined as false beliefs about rape, rapists, and the victims. Academic research focuses more on female rape, recent studies have explored some rape myths linked to male rape victims. Here are some of the male rape myths; men cannot be raped, homosexual men are the only the victims or perpetrators of rape, women cannot sexually abuse a man, men should be able to defend themselves, male rape only happens in prisons, and men are not emotionally affected by rape (Javaid, 2018).

In the previous sections, we also explored some of the issues of underreporting among rape victims. Male rape myths and underreporting largely correlate with each other, this is due to the fact that the rape myths listed above may prevent men from coming forward about their assault. Firstly men may

feel that what happened to them was not important enough to report and secondly that they will receive judgment from friends, family, society, and even the police (Hammond et al , 2016).

4.2 Institutional Issues

Male rape was mostly seen as an issue in imprisoned populations in the 1970s, and prisons were the first place that male rape gained some form of awareness. Male rape did not receive any form of public interest as it was only seen as a problem that a minuscule amount of people experienced. Due to this, it's believed that male rape in prisons was more concealed until more recently (Javaid, 2018). In most parts of the world, a large amount of male rape that occurs happens in prisons (Javaid, 2015). According to a charity called Male Survivors Trust, they estimate that around 80 percent of the male prison population have been victims of sexual abuse (including childhood abuse) in England and Wales (Male Survivors Trust, 2023).

However, this is just an estimate and empirical evidence of this on such a small scale that it remains unreliable. Because males are reluctant to disclose being raped and because it is challenging to conduct research on rape in prisons under conservative institutional frameworks, it is challenging to gather empirical evidence in prisons. However, even to this day, the ongoing myth that male rape only happens in prisons continues to persist in UK society. This myth is becoming a massive issue because it excludes male rape that occurs in the community; commonly, non-institutionalized rape has been viewed as consensual homosexual conduct (Javaid, 2015).

The author, Susan Brownmiller, wrote a book called, *'Against Our Will: Men, Women, and Rape'*, this book was written in 1975 and discussed the varied history of sexual violence. This book supported the argument that homosexual rape only occurred in prison and when discussing child sexual abuse only referred to girls, giving no examples of boys. The limitations of this book forewarned the struggle that historians and researchers would have encountered in this book's propositions. In early American history, the legal standpoint for sexual violence was that only women are raped. Male-on-male rape was not viewed as a crime because the literature- prohibited the act even if no consent was given, meaning that both parties were seen as committing an offence. Therefore, at that time there was no information available that studied assaults against men in institutional settings (Robertson, 2010). A global survey conducted in Boston 1994, found that many Americans had disciplinary and emotionless feelings towards prison rape, with 50 percent believing that prison rape is just the price that prisoners have to pay for their offending behaviour (Turchik & Edwards, 2012; Sennott, 1994).

4.3 Societal Issues

Societies' belief that rapes only happen in jail, and only homosexual men are raped has been found to be an individual notion of male rape (Struckman-Johnson & Struckman-Johnson, 1992). It's been suggested by academic researchers that societal notions about male rape fall far behind those of female rape, essentially, modern male rape perception is at the period that female rape perception was many years ago in regard to a person's understanding and ideology (Anderson, 2007; Donnelly and Kenyon, 1996).

A study examined the frequent occurrence of myths pertaining to male sexual assault, penetrative assault and rape within the general public selection. The aim of the study was to identify potential complications to the reporting of male sexual assaults and reasons for unwillingness to report. The study was comprised of 98 male participants (they were gathered using the snowballing method) residing in the United Kingdom, aged between 19-58. 83 percent of the participants were heterosexual, and 8 percent were homosexual, 7 percent were bisexual, and 2 percent identified as other. The participants completed an online questionnaire (in the format of the Likert scale). The study found that 60 percent believed that if a woman sexually attacks a man police would not regard it as serious (Hammond & Fewster, 2016).

Another study was conducted by Struckman-Johnson & Struckman-Johnson (1992) in the UK comprised of 119 undergraduate university students (of which 62 were women) who were asked to describe a representation of female and male rape. The study found that even though there are many changes, the current notions of female rape have not advanced as much as researchers initially thought and the participants are still attached to rape myths most known for female victims. However, there were still indications of male rape having a slight lag behind female rape. The theory that male rape was not characterized as a stranger rape stereotype (SRS) more than female rape was not established.

There were other factors that participants described in the study, there were descriptions of the victim's humiliation and guilt, penetration technicalities, the victim not wanting to report or not being believed, and the victim and offenders' sexual preferences. The participants also brought up the offender's physical strength, the victim's smaller frame compared to the offender, and the pain experienced by the victim after the assault. Participants described the offender and victim as being drunk. Many other factors brought up by the participants portrayed inaccurate and storybook thoughts of male rape (Chapleau et al, 2008). Examples of this are participants believing that an ideal victim should have a smaller stature than the offender, that the offender and victim are homosexual, and that

the offender is only influenced by sexual desire. Within some of the scripts, there were some signs of homophobic language and contents some of which were unintended by nature (Anderson, 2007).

The assumption that men are supposed to attain a certain level of masculinity grouped with a worry of being seen as homosexual or feminine may encourage young men and boys to exhibit masculine actions as a part of impression control. For example, becoming sexually active and 'getting together' with as many females as possible, just to prove to other men that they are straight and manly. These actions are also performed when male assault and rape victims are trying to regain their masculinity after being exploited in ways that normally happen with females (Weiss, 2010).

4.4 Media Issues

According to Cohen (2014), the media holds a sense of power and acceptance over the world. It holds the strength to validate the information of the general population while creating and refining it. Cohen also argued that the media is a crucial way in which society learns and through this social learning process, it warps people into being familiar with typical practices. Essentially, it is more than reasonable to assume that the media also has the ability to shape society's actions and beliefs toward male rape (Javaid, 2015).

Ancient Greek legends (like the one of Chrysippus and Laius) and Biblical narratives (such as the males attempts to rape a pair of male angels and the attack on Lot that his daughters committed) all contain stories and descriptions of male rape that date back a few thousand years. In more recent times, media, in particular TV, has probably had a significant role in raising public awareness of male rape because it is thought that media coverage is the best way to obtain information about crimes (e.g., Fields & Jerin, 1996), in spite of the fact that male rape is rarely represented in the general media (Turchik & Edwards, 2012).

An example of this is from the film *Pulp Fiction* and another film called *Deliverance*. These two films are globally known and watched and displayed rape scenes that show the offender as being poor and rustic southern men. This kind of portrayal advances the myth that male rape only happens in a poor, uncivilized area with 'hillbilly' men (Scarce, 1997). We know this is not true because, in the case of Sinaga, he was a typical-looking student, well dressed, appeared harmless, and from a wealthy background (BBC, 2021). The assaults within the films are crude and the crazed sex drive replaces men as sexual targets when no women are around (just like in cases of prisons), but it also distinguishes an embodiment of bestiality. In the film, *Deliverance*, the character called Bobby is degraded as an outsider

and an animal, it takes a sophisticated man that wandered away from nature and lost his sense of heightened manliness and attempted masculine efforts to have sexual dominance over his own body (Scarce, 1997).

According to Wlodarz and his analysis of Hollywood films, even though anal sex is hardly depicted in films when it comes to male rape there were numerous times anal rape was depicted during the 1990s. He believed that films like *Deliverance* illustrate 'male rape revenge films' where the man who was victimised goes on an extreme journey to recover their feeling of manliness and reinstate patriarchy and that homosexual men are presented as the fall guy or person to be blamed. Many films that depict male rape often encourage the perceptions of the public that male rape and homosexuality are solely connected. Whenever male rape is shown in a fictitious setting, it normally takes place in prison (Wlodarz, 2001).

Chapter 5: Trauma

5.1 Introduction

This section will be highlighting some of the cognitive trauma and diagnoses that male rape victims experience. This section will also explore some behavioural and childhood traumas through empirical research.

5.2 Cognitive Impact

Signs of psychological trauma; denial, guilt, shame, flashback to the assault, fantasising about revenge, feeling scared to lose control in certain situations, and uncontrollable behaviour (Cook & Hodo, 2013). When applying the element of trauma to the criminal justice system it is helpful for those within the system to acknowledge defence circuitry and the neurobiology of trauma. This gives an insight into how victims react in menacing situations, especially in situations such as violent sexual assaults (Haskell & Randall, 2019).

There are many ramifications to someone being victimised. More recently the psychological and emotional effects of someone being victimised have gained a lot more awareness. This is due to various amounts of victims showing indications of post-traumatic stress. Symptoms of post-traumatic stress tend to fade within a few weeks or even months, but for the most part, individuals who experience severe or repeated trauma need to find appropriate therapy (Gavrielides, 2021). The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM-5) describes health diagnoses for people who suffer from trauma from incidents such as rape and assault. The diagnoses provided list, acute stress disorder and PTSD. There are other diagnoses specific to rape that are not mentioned, such as rape-related PTSD and rape trauma syndrome (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Having more specific diagnoses helps healthcare workers to list some symptoms and provide the appropriate care (Gavrielides, 2021).

Here are some examples listed below of behaviour associated with rape trauma symptoms and rape-related PTSD: Those suffering rape trauma syndrome tend to feel, humiliation, suicidal, revengeful and suffer from reoccurring nightmares. They can also display behavioural reactions such as abusing drugs and alcohol. A more undetectable reaction is to not disclose their assault to anyone or completely deny it. Rape-related PTSD seems to be more cognitive. Victims suffer from flashbacks to the event, nightmares, they can become socially withdrawn and also display signs of denial. There are also elements of heightened psychological arousal, such as being easily startled (Ellis, 2002).

A study conducted by Voller et al (2015) gathered data from 1,872 veterans who fought in the Gulf War. These participants all applied for PTSD disability benefits. The participants completed a survey that questioned the history of child abuse, and sexual assault while they were serving. The survey also determined male rape myths were present among the participants and some symptoms of PTSD and depression. The participant's scores indicated that 76.4 percent of them met the standards for PTSD, 44.6 percent met the standard for depression, and 24.7 percent reported having a history of sexual abuse. The findings revealed that participants suffering from sexual trauma in the past were statistically significant and highly correlated with psychiatric symptoms. This was also the case for self-efficacy and a decrease in emotions (Voller et al, 2015).

5.3 Behavioural Impact

Types of physical trauma; Anal tearing which would need medical attention, risk of subjection to sexually transmitted diseases (such as HIV, chlamydia and gonorrhoea), loss of memory, insomnia, nausea, and stomach aches (Cook & Hodo, 2013). Not all traumatic incidents need to be violent, an individual's sense of safety can be violated and cause trauma, it's also important to acknowledge that trauma is subjective, and everyone's response to a traumatic event is different (Kammerer & Mazelis, 2006; Haskell & Randall, 2019).

Research conducted on victims revealed that many say that they froze or felt like they could not do anything, but why is this? (Haskell & Randall, 2019). Gray (1988) argued that fight, flight, freeze, and fright are behaviours that naturally occur among organisms when threatened. However, Bracha et al. (2004) argue that the idea of flight or fight is outdated. Brache expanded on this point and believed that freezing happens when an animal has noticed a predator is around. In these events the animal will become completely still and slow its heart rate down, preparing itself for a fight or flight reaction (Bracha, 2004). In humans this is referred to as Tonic immobility (TI) this is when a person becomes immobile, shakes, experiences chills (cold sensation), experiences a reduction of pain, and loses their voice. There is evidence that indicates that male victims experience TI when they are being raped or sexually assaulted. Men normally report freezing. Mezey and King's (1989) study gathered 22 men who have been Tonic immobility (TI) this is when a person becomes immobile, shakes, experiences chills (cold sensation), experiences a reduction of pain, and loses their voice. There is evidence that indicates that male victims experience TI when they are being raped or sexually assaulted. Men normally report freezing. Mezey and King's (1989) study gathered 22 men who have been sexually assaulted. 63 percent of heterosexual males and 59 percent of homosexual males reported freezing (Coxell & King, 2010).

5.4 The Overlooked Trauma of Boys

Childhood sexual abuse is quite a complicated area to try and research, this is due to the humiliation and shame that encompass it (Watkins & Bentovim, 1992). Rape is one of the most under reported crimes, in America 63 percent of sexual assaults are not reported to the police. Out of that, only 12 percent of child sexual abuse is reported to the police (Hanson et al, 1999).

There continues to be a clear gap around this area of sexual crimes and boys who have experienced sexual abuse often lag behind research that is conducted on girls. This is because sexual abuse among boys was viewed as a rare occurrence, and many did not believe that boys who experienced abuse suffered from any crucial effects or hindered development (Garnefski & Diekstra, 1997).

Rogers and Terry (1984) stated that detectable reactions that they saw were somewhat unique to male victims and seemed to be connected to the homoerotic innuendos of sexual contact in concurrence with distinctive societal presumptions of behaviours for boys. The types of responses that occurred often were listed were the feeling of scepticism and anxiety about their sexual orientation; unacceptable advances in asserting masculinity; and the recounting of their assault. A study by Sebold (1987) was conducted in the US and estimated that between 46,000-96,000, boys are molested each year. The study gathered 22 therapists who specialise in working with male children who are sexually abused.

Another study was conducted by Garnefski & Arendson (1997) on 745 secondary school students in the Netherlands (594 girls 151 boys) aged 12-19. These participants reported a background of sexual abuse. Another sample of 745 students was matched and had no history of sexual abuse. Boys and girls who were sexually abused were contrasted and assigned to four problem categories: Hostile/offending behaviours, risks to addiction, unregulated emotions, and suicidal behaviour. The purpose of the study was to look at boys and girls who were sexually abused and boys and girls who were not and compare the data. The finding revealed two vital conclusions. Firstly, it stated that children who had a past of sexual abuse reported much more unregulated emotions, issues with behaviour, and suicidal tendencies as a consequence, compared to children who had no past of sexual abuse. Secondly, while this result is valid for boys and girls, the results are more striking for boys. An example of this was the data for suicidal tendencies, it was documented that girls who were sexually abused were 4.8 times more likely to display suicidal tendencies compared to girls who were not abused. Boys who were sexually abused were 10.8 times more likely to display suicidal tendencies compared to boys who were not abused (Garnefski & Diekstra, 1997). Why is this? The number may reflect this due to the fact that

boys are more likely to be sexually abused by someone of the same sex compared to girls. This suggests that combined with feelings of anger, humiliation, and embarrassment boys have to face, they also additionally question and experience anxiety about their homosexuality because of the aforementioned societal issues / prejudices (Bagley et al, 1994). The repercussions can potentially be much worse for boys. There were some limitations to the Garnefski & Arendson (1997) study, it is possible that there could have been some formed biases of false positive and false negative accounts of sexual abuse. However, if this was the case it wouldn't have been able to explain the results (Garnefski & Diekstra, 1997).

Unfortunately, in most cases, those who have been sexually abused have been abused by individuals in positions of authority. This could be family members, teachers, pastors, and sports coaches. Fater and Mullanney (2000) study revealed that on top of the cognitive impacts that sexual abuse on children can have, victims feel immensely betrayed and often become detached from their relationship with the church and in some cases become atheists. This can detrimentally affect people who were deeply ingrained in their religion and normally turned to it in times of grief and distress. Gavrielides (2012) also referred to this as spiritual trauma which challenges the victim's spiritual identity and political distress (Gavrielides, 2021).

Chapter 6: Victim Blaming

6.1 Introduction

In this chapter discussions of male victim blaming will be compared to response to female assaults. A look into secondary victimisation that male rape victims have to face after their initial assault will be discussed and finally how homosexual victimisation occurs from populations of men and even public sectors.

Not as many crimes evoke as much disbelief, shaming and victim blaming as allegations of rape and sexual abuse, as acknowledged a lot of this stems from rape myths and fuels the idea that the victim wanted it, deserved it, or encouraged their own assault. Regarding men, it's often assumed that only women are raped, and that 'real' men cannot be raped - which of course is an incorrect stance on the issue, as explained in the previous chapters (Davies & McCarthy, 2003). Victim blaming often makes men feel shamed and reluctant to share their experiences. Weiss (2010) explains that some men who are viewed as strong and able to defend themselves are embarrassed to acknowledge publicly that they were overpowered and assaulted sexually. This reemphasises the unique gendered victimisation that male survivors of rape face.

Victims of rape also tend to blame themselves for events that have occurred, Brochman (1991) argues that for the case of some male victims, the blame emerges from believing that they gave permission to the rapist. Victims of male rape endure similar ignorant myths that women experience which is that they enjoyed being raped. Complexing this issue, some men who have been assaulted believe that they were not raped because they became sexually aroused or ejaculated. It is important to emphasise that this does not equal consent and therefore, of course, such acts are morally abhorrent. Indeed, these reactions are reflexive psychological responses and do not equate to the victim enjoying the experience or wanting it to happen (Cook & Hodo, 2013). Further complexing this issue, some perpetrators purposefully try to get the victims to ejaculate as this exemplifies their control over the victim's body. Understandably, this part of the assault can cause immense stress and embarrassment for the victim. Male rape victims may be confused by their bodies' response as it is often associated that ejaculation is an orgasm, this also can contribute to the hesitancy of wanting to report the assault (Groth & Burgess, 1980).

6.2 Men vs Women

Many academic researchers are not going to argue that most of the offenders of sex crimes are male. However, it's important to acknowledge that there are crime surveys and empirical researchers that have mostly been in tune with showing that the amount of females who are perpetrators of sexual crimes is not insignificant (Oliver, 2007).

There are many cultural beliefs that influence a lack of accountability for female offenders of sexual crime. For example, when underage males are sexually involved with a female it is deemed as something to be celebrated or merited, there is a large stigma about females penetrating a man, and often women are sexually depicted as blameless and peaceful (Scarce, 1997). (This is, of course, a myth that has been previously explored in the prior chapters). When comparing male and female sexual offenders research has shown that there are some clear differences and similarities. Some of the differences stated are that female perpetrators were more likely to have suffered from harsh and reoccurring sexual abuse when they were aged 6 or younger, they were more likely to have been exposed to incestuous relationships, were more likely to try and commit suicide, and be diagnosed with PTSD. The similarities they shared were some psychological disorders such as depression, suicidal tendencies, and anxiety, they were also similar in ethnicity and age (Williams & Bierie, 2014).

Research conducted by Pollard et al (1992) found that women make more judgments toward female victims of sexual assault than men do. This is surprising considering that is typically believed that men are the ones who blame female victims, and this is the argument used especially within the feminist movement (Pollard, 1992). It is also important to acknowledge that this study is quite outdated. However, it is also the case that men blame male victims more than women do. A study conducted by Davies et al, on judgments towards male rape victims who suffered sexual abuse, found that men are more likely to blame male victims when the assault consisted of forced fellatio and even when the victims were unconscious (2008).

The fact that men blame male rape victims the most correlates with the theory that they are living up to their sex role expectations (Weiss, 2010). These expectations are inscribed through cultural views about masculinity and are supported by men on a greater level in comparison to women. Even so, not all studies present the idea that male victims receive more blame than female victims. Howard (1984) believed that there are no differences between how men and women are blamed. He used the term general blame which mentions elements that do not categorise the type of blame. General blame was used in studies by many other researchers such as Schneider, et al (1994) and McCaul et al. (1990),

these studies found that female victims were blamed more than men. However, the female offender was seen to be less guilty and given a lower prison sentence compared to the male offender of the female victim. It was explained that this occurred due to the general population's stereotypes about men being more physically superior and authoritative, the thought that a man can be mentally affected by rape is not often considered, with more compassion shown towards the female victim's emotions (Davies & Rogers, 2006).

It is argued that men are not as likely to receive compassion and comfort when the offender of sexual assault is a female. Studies showed that 47 percent of men feel that men who are sexually abused by a woman would be sexually aroused by the incident. In academic settings, college students (male and female) are much more likely to think that men cannot be raped by a woman compared to a man being raped by another man (Mitchell et al, 1999). This mindset seems to be mirrored in military environments, there are much fewer women serving and of those serving many do not take part in combat positions. There is also the mindset that women are to be captivated and protected rather than be seen as dangerous. So, therefore, the thought that a man can be raped by someone deemed as fragile and delicate seems to contradict the powerful military recognition (O'Brien & Shoemaker, 2015).

6.3 Secondary Victimization

Though there have been many legal changes, public interest, and academic research into male victimisation, the public and even public services such as the police and military still share some ignorant misconceptions (Lowe & Rogers, 2017). Recent studies found that male veterans in the military that were victims of sexual assault, were introduced to deficient treatment when they tried to get help from governmental and voluntary agencies. The researcher noted that the subjects of the study suffered from 'secondary victimisation' (Javaid, 2015).

Secondary victimisation is like an incidental assault that occurs due to the responses of governmental bodies and individuals to the victims. There are different kinds of secondary victimisation, victim blaming, abusive language or behaviour by the police, health workers, or other agencies that come into contact with the victim after their assault. The origin of secondary victimisation is prominent in cases of female rape, in a study many females reported that going to medical, mental, and legal systems increases the trauma. This study also connected links between post-traumatic stress and secondary victimisation (Javaid, 2015). It is not often that male rape victims are able to pick which practitioner they want based on their gender. Male rape victims tend to want female practitioners due to the fact they feel uncomfortable disclosing their personal experiences to another man, especially when it's after

a recent assault. Secondary rape is experienced by the victims when they are required to be vulnerable and give in to another man after their assault (Ellis, 2002). When the victim feels like they have no control and authority and do not have a say in their treatment, this can enhance the chances that the victim will relive their traumatic experience the same feeling that they felt during their assault. Institutional services tend to be male dominated as well as some voluntary services this can have an effect on the way that the victim's needs are structurally being unmet (Javaid, 2017). The idea of secondary victimisation happening in police practices may be because they are not taken seriously or believed. This can create a feeling of shame and guilt in the victim. It's important to acknowledge that when a victim encounters this kind of reaction from the police it becomes an ongoing issue that seems to have no resolution for the victim (Javaid, 2016).

6.4 Homosexual Victimisation

Various studies have examined the results of sexual preference on characteristics among male victims of a male offender. The studies revealed that regardless of the assault circumstances, homosexual victims were deemed to be more at fault or to blame in comparison to heterosexual victims. It is rationalised that the homosexual essence of male rape (even though non-consensual) motivates homophobic elements that end in victim blaming or other hostile elements. The results that were revealed showing that men blame male victims for rape support this proposal. On average heterosexual men are much more homophobic than women. This indicates that homosexual men are viewed negatively in certain circumstances not only in sexual assault incidences but also in domestic violence (Davies & McCarthy, 2004; Davies et al., 2001; Hammond et al., 2016).

When police are responding to male rape victims it is normally wrongfully assumed that the victim is homosexual due to the sexual nature that male rape is associated with, this heightens the chances of homophobic responses being set among male rape victims who are viewed as gay (Hine et al, 2021). A study conducted in England gathered 25 police officers and practitioners. Additionally, 45 participants were gathered to complete a questionnaire, these participants were of the same occupations. The people who were interviewed did not complete the questionnaire. The aim of this study was to highlight issues with how police and practitioners deal with rape cases. The finding of the study supported the theory that police and practitioners still have dated views and perceptions towards male rape. The study found that there was still a faulty response from the police when dealing with male rape victims, the underlying police culture still heavily influences officer's conclusions and accusations regarding rape cases, and some officers often assume that male rape cases are falsely reported. This creates a major

gap in potential reporting numbers, as the false report is not recorded as a crime and therefore misrepresents the perspective when male rape actually occurs (Javaid, 2016).

Even within the military, there is a leisurely change in perspectives about homosexuality. The attitudes in the military determine that homosexuality puts other people in jeopardy. There is a toxic attitude that homosexual people are the offenders and put other soldiers at risk. Therefore, there is a fear within the military among soldiers that if they are sexually assaulted by another man in the military they will be viewed as homosexual. Being characterised as homosexual does not hold as a legitimate reason for discharge, however, it still unfortunately conveys negative implications in military territories (Voller et al, 2015). Again, this is another unique gendered injustice experienced by male rape survivors.

O'Brien & Shoemaker (2015) conduct group sessions with men who have been victims of sexual abuse. A frequent discussion that occurred in the group were about sexual trauma. Many men expressed having concerns about being feminized and discussions of what it means to be a real man were brought up with some even offering advice to one another. One of the participants who was a Vietnam veteran said that he created a hyper-masculine identity being an out-law biker. He expressed that his assault led to him bleeding from his rectum a few days after it occurred, he associated this with shame and felt like he was bleeding like a woman and no longer felt like a man. These group sessions reveal that men question their sexual orientation and identity as a man and most men take it to the furthest point by parodying versions of their masculinity to create an identity. An example of this is the revelation by men in the groups, discussing hyper-sexual actions that they engage in such as sleeping with a subsequent number of women just to prove their straightness and masculinity (O'Brien & Shoemaker, 2015).

Chapter 7: Conclusion

This dissertation has been able to identify an important social justice issue: the significant amount of under-reporting issues that are relevant to this day in the UK and other countries. This was achieved by analysing the Crime Survey of England and Wales which revealed that there are still inconsistencies with the data gathered and that the number of reports is not reflective of the number of sexual assaults, this creates a large gap in this field (CSEW, 2023). This research project revealed that there are numerous studies supporting the fact the general population shares misconceptions about male rape which discourages victims to come forward out of fear of being judged (Hammond et al, 2016).

There is also a lack of knowledge among men about what male rape is and what defined them as being raped, this leaves many men feeling that their assault was not rape and stops them from coming forward (Javaid, 2018). Other areas that were examined in the research proposal revealed that rape myths and underreporting largely correlate with each other and that many of the societal stereotypes about male rape are the sole reason why men refuse to come forward (Hammond et al , 2016). Within the project victim blaming and trauma were key areas to be explored. This project highlighted that victims who are often blamed tend to be homosexual, and it is often assumed that male victims of rape are homosexual. This mindset has spilled into the police culture and other fields which detrimentally affects the way that male rape cases are handled (Hine et al, 2021).

Studies revealed that men are more likely to blame male victims, in fact, men are more likely to blame the victim in general (Davies et al, 2008). This highlights that there are issues with the cultural norms that deem men to be physically stronger and therefore should be able to fend off the offender. The case of Sinaga shows that no matter how strong a man appears to be they can easily be subdued when drugged (BBC, 2021). The vast number of legal changes still have not resolved the issues of how society reacts to male rape, this has influenced military and government bodies leading to victims experiencing secondary victimisation (Javaid, 2015). The effects of secondary victimisation re-traumatise the individual and creates mistrust of police and other sectors. Secondary victimisation is also due to victim blaming, which public sectors have been guilty of.

Societal norms have stopped many men and boys from looking for help. Western men are often told that crying is a sign of weakness (Javaid, 2015). And that to be a man you need to display hypermasculine behaviours. This has resulted in them feeling uniquely humiliated when they

experience something that removes their sense of masculinity and control (Weiss, 2010). Academic researchers have more recently discussed how early childhood trauma can alter someone's life and how they come to terms with the abuse that they faced. Researchers have also highlighted the issues within society that lead victims to doubt that they will receive the appropriate help.

Some organisations are offering a light at the end of the tunnel, for example, the Global campaign called 'Start by believing' was created in America and was initiated by End Violence Against Women International (EVAWI). Although this campaign is targeted more towards women its message is still reflective of male rape cases. This campaign highlights the way in which certain public sectors should approach and speak to a victim of rape. It proves that victims are looking for someone who can listen to them; can tolerate the graphic things that they may or may not disclose; someone who has great knowledge about what they are experiencing and most importantly someone who visualises that their story is true. All these elements contribute towards someone feeling more confident in talking and providing details about their assault (Start by believing, 2023). The language used among victims of rape are very important, when speaking to a victim of sexual assault it's important for police to not use words such as 'alleged' and 'reported' when mentioning the crime. Using this type of language creates the idea that there is uncertainty and suspicion in their story. As an alternative police should show regard and empathy. However, empathy is not something that is easily taught by academics. But it's an expertise that can be mastered and refined (Haskell & Randall, 2019). When we are able to allow men to share their stories in an environment that is accepting and safe with no judgment, we are then able to put in place more protective systems for men and boys (Kabbara, 2020).

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